

Halogenation of (a) 2-Hydroxy-4-methyl quinolines and (b) 2,4-Dihydroxy quinolines: (3-Halogenated carbostyrils)

G. H. PATEL and C. M. MEHTA

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, M.S. University of Baroda, Baroda

Manuscript received 2 June 1969; revised 8 April 1972; accepted 14 November 1972

The present work was undertaken with a view to obtain the products on cyclisation of mono halogenated derivatives of (i) acetoacetic arylamides and (ii) malon mono arylamides and also to prepare the halogenated derivatives on direct halogenation of carbostyrils in order to confirm the position in which the halogen atom enters the ring.

IN earlier communication¹ only the bromination of quinolinediols was reported. In the present investigation the direct halogenation of carbostyrils and the cyclisation of α -halogenated arylamides have been carried out. Further, α -halogenated acetoacetarylamides and α -halogenated malonmonoarylamides have been cyclised using a mixture of acetic anhydride and con. sulphuric acid in the case of the former and using polyphosphoric acid in the case of the latter. The 3-chloro, 3-bromo or 3-iodo carbostyrils obtained are found to be identical on direct comparison with the compounds obtained on direct halogenation of carbostyrils.

Experimental

(a) 3-chloro-4-methyl (or 4-hydroxy) carbostyril : 4-methyl (or 4-hydroxy) carbostyril (0.01m) was dissolved in 15 ml. of glacial acetic acid in presence of a trace of iodine as catalyst, to which was added sulphuryl chloride (0.01M) in cold. The reaction mixture was stirred for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr., The separated product crystallised from alcohol.

(b) 3-bromo-4-methyl (or 4-hydroxy) carbostyril : 4-methyl (or 4-hydroxy) carbostyril (0.01m) was dissolved in 25 ml. of glacial acid in presence of a trace of iodine as catalyst, to which 20% solution of bromine in acetic acid (8.0 ml) was slowly added with

(where X = Cl, Br or I; Y = CH₃ in III_a and y = OH in III_b; R = phenyl, tolyl, xylyl or naphthyl group).

TABLE-I 3-SUBSTITUTED 4-METHYL CARBOSTYRILS

Sr. No.	Compound	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	%Halogen		%Carbon		%Hydrogen	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
E = (3-bromo-2-hydroxy-) D = (3-iodo-2-hydroxy-) K = (3-chloro-2-hydroxy-) Q = (quinoline)										
1.	B-4,6-dimethyl-Q	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ONBr	282	87.7	31.35	31.74	52.88	52.38	3.92	3.97
2.	B-4,8-dimethyl-Q	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ONBr	255	92.4	31.56	31.74	—	—	—	—
3.	B-4,6,8-trimethyl-Q	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ ONBr	265	74.8	29.75	30.07	—	—	—	—
4.	B-6-ethoxy-4-methyl-Q	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ NBr	252	80.0	28.19	28.37	—	—	—	—
5.	K-4,8-dimethyl-Q	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ONCl	205	70.6	22.16	21.69	—	—	—	—
6.	K-4-methyl-benzo-Q(7:8)	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ ONCl	380	53.3	14.68	14.57	—	—	—	—
7.	K-4-methyl-benzo-Q(5:6)	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ ONCl	370	62.2	14.75	14.57	—	—	—	—
8.	D-4-methyl-Q	C ₁₀ H ₈ ONI	291	75.0	44.69	44.51	—	—	—	—
9.	D-4,8-dimethyl-Q	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ONI	232	63.6	42.28	42.47	—	—	—	—
10.	D-4,6-dimethyl-Q	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ONI	280	73.3	42.13	42.47	—	—	—	—
11.	D-4,6,7-trimethyl-Q	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ ONI	273	68.4	40.76	40.58	—	—	—	—

All m.ps. are uncorrected.

stirring. The reaction mixture, on dilution with water, gave the product, which was crystallised from alcohol.

(c) *3-iodo-4-methyl carbostyryl*: 4-methyl carbostyryl (0.05m) was dissolved in minimum quantity of hot alcohol to which iodine crystals (0.04m) and con. aqueous solution of iodic acid (0.01M) were added. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 hr. and on dilution with water, it gave the product which was filtered and crystallised from alcohol. All attempts to iodinate 2,4-quinolinediols were unsuccessful.

(d) Above mentioned 3-halogenated quinoline derivatives in (a), (b) and (c) were also prepared by the cyclisation of α -halogenated acetoacetyl amides and α -halogenated malonmonoarylamides with acetic anhydride and conc. sulphuric acid in the former case and with PPA in the latter case. Mixed m.p.s. of the above 3-halogenated quinoline derivatives (carbostyryls) were not depressed.

Halogenated quinolines listed in Table 1 and Table 2 as well as the halogenated substituted amines, listed in Table 3 are prepared for the first time; whereas the other requisite amides are prepared by the known methods.^{4,5}

TABLE-2 3-SUBSTITUTED 4-HYDROXY CARBOSTYRILS

H = (-2,4-dihydroxyquinoline-)

Srl. No.	Compound	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	%Halogen		%Carbon		%Hydrogen	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	3-Bromo-6-methyl-H	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ NBr	260	75.6	31.73	31.50	47.22	47.24	3.40	3.15
2.	3-Bromo-7-methyl-H	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ NBr	237	75.4	31.34	31.50	—	—	—	—
3.	3-Bromo-6-chloro-H	C ₉ H ₈ O ₂ NBrCl	262	61.5	—	—	—	—	—	—
4.	3-Bromo-6-methoxy-H	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₃ NBr	256	62.8	29.63	29.62	44.82	44.44	3.35	3.15
5.	3-Bromo-6,7-dimethyl-H	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ NBr	255	73.6	29.40	29.70	—	—	—	—
6.	3-Chloro-6-methyl-H	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₂ NCl	296	68.5	16.36	16.90	—	—	—	—
7.	3-Chloro-6-methoxy-H	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₃ NCl	268	60.5	15.53	15.74	53.51	53.20	3.52	3.54
8.	3-Chloro-6,7-dimethyl-H	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ NCl	228	69.4	15.54	15.89	—	—	—	—
9.	3-Bromo-2,4-dihydroxybenzoquinoline (5 : 6).	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₂ NBr	270	73.8	27.88	27.60	—	—	—	—

All m.ps. are uncorrected.

TABLE-3 MONOHALO MALON MONO ARYLAMIDES

B = (Monobromo malon mono-)

K = (Monochloro malon mono-)

D = (Monoiodo malon mono-)

Sr. No.	Compound	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	%Halogen		%Nitrogen	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	B- <i>p</i> -toluidide	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Br	190	65.1	—	—	10.51	10.33
2.	B- <i>m</i> -toluidide	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Br	172	62.5	29.73	29.52	—	—
3.	B- <i>p</i> -chloroanilide	C ₉ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂ ClBr	180	65.88	—	—	14.30	14.35
4.	B- <i>p</i> -anisidide	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₂ Br	165	67.31	28.15	27.87	—	—
5.	B-1 : 3 : 4-xylydide	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Br	172	75.0	28.04	27.97	—	—
6.	B-B-naphthylamide	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Br	215	70.2	—	—	8.75	9.12
7.	K- <i>p</i> -toluidide	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	140	67.7	15.62	15.74	—	—
8.	K- <i>p</i> -anisidide	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	142	67.3	—	—	11.30	11.54
9.	K-1 : 3 : 4-xylydide	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	148	69.1	15.13	14.76	—	—
10.	D-anilide	C ₉ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ I	165	67.5	41.76	41.44	—	—
11.	D- <i>p</i> -toluidide	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ I	175	79.1	40.35	39.93	—	—

All m.ps. are uncorrected.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the M.S. University of Baroda for giving facilities to carry out this work.

References

1. C. M. MEHTA and G. H. PATEL, *Current Sci.*, 1961, 30, 15.
2. B. P. BANGDIWALA and C. M. DESAI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 30, 655.
3. G. H. PATEL and C. M. MEHTA, *J. Sci., Ind. Res.*, 1960, 19B, 436.
4. C. M. MEHTA, J. M. TRIVEDI and G. H. PATEL, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 460.
5. M. D. AVASARE, M. L. SHAH and N. M. SHETH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 29, 709.